

Enhancing Representation of Changes in IDE with Refactorings Information

1. How many years of professional development experience do you have?
 - Less than one year
 - 1 - 2
 - 3 - 5
 - 6 - 10
 - 11+

Block 1: General questions about the inspection of refactoring changes

2. How often do you need to review refactoring changes?

Never Rarely Sometimes Often Very often

3. Do you pay special attention to refactoring changes during code review?

Do not know Definitely no Rather no Rather yes Definitely yes

4. If you pay special attention to refactoring changes, could you please tell why?

5. Does having to identify refactorings in code changes slow down the code review process?

Definitely no Rather no Sometimes Rather yes Definitely yes

6. Would you like to have a possibility to review refactoring changes separately from other changes in code diffs?

Do not know Definitely no Rather no Rather yes Definitely yes

Block 2: Feedback about the plugin

7. How helpful is the textual information about refactorings in code changes provided by the plugin?

Not at all helpful Unhelpful More or less helpful Helpful Very helpful

8. How accurately does the plugin identify refactorings?

Very inaccurately Not accurately More or less accurately Accurately
Very accurately

9. Is the visualization of refactorings provided by the plugin clear to you?

Not at all clear Not clear More or less clear Clear Very clear

10. If the visualization of some refactoring types is not clear, please specify these types.

11. Does the plugin interrupt your interaction with IDE somehow? If yes, please, tell us how.

12. If you have any ideas about the ways to simplify the process of inspecting code changes in the IDE, feel free to share them with us!